

Study on the valorisation of laminated waste as radon barriers for indoor spaces

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ABSTRACT

Nowadays, there is a severe problem with waste generation, especially with single-use packaging. Although the trend is to try to recycle or reuse this waste, a significant amount still ends up in landfills, which represents a serious environmental problem. This waste includes laminated materials, which are difficult to recycle because the polymeric material and aluminium layers cannot be separated easily. This work proposes the study of the valorisation of several laminated wastes as radon barriers for indoor spaces due to the similarity in composition between these waste and commercial radon barriers. For this purpose, the diffusion coefficient of laminated wastes composed of polymeric and aluminium materials, with thicknesses between 70 and 500 μm , has been calculated using a modification of the ISO/TS 11665–13:2017 standard. The diffusion coefficients obtained are in the range of 10^{-12} and 10^{-14} m^2/s , a reduction of radon concentration of over 90%, and a high radon resistance is achieved in all cases. These results show the excellent capacity of these materials to slow down radon and indicate that these wastes could be reused to manufacture radon barriers giving a new life to these materials and contributing to sustainable development and a circular economy.

1. Introduction

The use of plastics is globally extended to the point that 460 million tonnes were used in 2019 (OECD, 2022). The packaging industry is the sector that uses the highest amount of plastic, both at world level (31.02%) (OECD, 2022), European level (39.6%) (Plastics Europe, 2020) and Spanish level (36%) (EsPlásticos, 2021). Fig. 1 shows the use of plastics by sector.

Almost 99.5% of the plastic of single-use manufactured as packaging ends as waste in less than a year, which is a serious environmental problem. Almost half of those wastes worldwide were landfilled, and less than 20% and 10% were incinerated and recycled, respectively (OECD, 2022). However, in the last years, the trend changed at the European level due to Directive 2018/852, which indicates that waste prevention is the best way to reduce its impact. Furthermore, it encourages Member States to implement measures to promote reusable packaging use and otherwise recycle or recover packaging waste (European Union, 2018). Nowadays, 40.64% of packaging waste is being recycled or 36.55% incinerated; but still 22.81% of waste is landfilled. Spain has a 51.48% recycling rate for packaging waste, while energy recovery is only

15.38%; still, a third of the waste ended up in landfills (Eurostat, n.d.). Fig. 2 shows the end-of-life treatment of packaging wastes by region.

Most packaging is produced in multilayer materials, both polymer-polymer and polymer-aluminium. These laminated materials are difficult to recycle as the different layers of polymeric materials and aluminium are difficult to separate, although techniques such as delamination or selective dissolution-precipitation are available (Kaiser et al., 2018; Xie et al., 2016).

The limitation of these techniques is that they are applied to specific multilayer materials for which the composition is known, which makes it challenging to apply on a general level and if solvents are used, they are harmful to the environment and generate another waste stream that needs to be treated. In addition, these techniques also have low efficiencies and high separation times, which hinder industrial viability and economic efficiency (Kaiser et al., 2018).

This same polymer-polymer or polymer-aluminium blend composition is found in commercial radon barriers. These barriers are installed between the ground and the foundations of buildings to prevent radon exhaled from the ground from entering and concentrating. As radon is a naturally occurring radioactive gas classified as carcinogenic by the

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Fig. 1. Use of plastics by sector at the global, European and Spanish levels (EsPlásticos, 2021; OECD, 2022; Plastics Europe, 2020).

Fig. 2. Quantity of packaging waste treated by region and end-of-life treatment (Eurostat, OECD, 2022).

WHO (World Health Organization, 2009), many countries set concentration limits and mitigation techniques to protect people from the risks related to the presence of radon (Holmgren and Arvela, 2012).

Installing radon barriers is one of the most cost-effective techniques to mitigate the radon concentration in new buildings (Khan et al., 2019). They must be airtight and continuous (Pacheco-Torgal, 2012). The diffusion coefficient is used to determine which materials are suitable for preventing the flow of radon. This parameter indicates the ease with which radon passes through the barrier, so the lower the diffusion coefficient, the better the protection provided by the barrier (Jiránek et al., 2008).

To ensure good radon protection, several conditions are proposed that radon barriers must meet. For example, in Spain, according to the Technical Building Code established by the legal regulations, the barriers must be at least 2 mm thick and have a diffusion coefficient below

$10^{-11} \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$ (Spanish Ministry for Transport Mobility and the Urban Agenda, 2019).

Given the similarity in composition between multilayer packaging waste and radon barriers, a preliminary study is proposed to determine their potential use as radon barriers for indoor spaces to give a second life to these wastes and contribute to sustainable development and the circular economy.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Samples

The samples were taken from ordinary household waste: liquid packaging boards and packaging for various foods. All samples consist of multiple layers of polymeric materials and/or aluminium, as shown in Table 1. The thickness of the samples was measured before the radon diffusion tests with a micrometre (Baxlo Precision, model 3006, with a $10 \mu\text{m}$ accuracy).

A characterisation of the profile of the samples was carried out with a field emission scanning electron microscope (FESEM), model ULTRA 55 from Zeiss and Oxford Instruments and with the magnifying lens, model MZ APO from Leica Microsystems, located in the Electron Microscopy Service of the UPV. The images obtained are shown in Fig. 4. With the FESEM images, a platinum coating and a magnification between 125x and 1000x was used, while with the magnifying lens, the magnification was between 40x and 80x.

2.2. Experimental set-up

The experimental set-up consists of two identical, sealed AISI 316L stainless steel chambers, designed according to the recommendations of ISO/TS 11665:13 (ISO, 2017). Each chamber has a volume of 0.801 L, and the test area is 78.5 cm^2 . A sealed pitchblende stone with an activity of 1.469 kBq is used as the radon source, which is placed inside the bottom chamber, named source container. The upper chamber, the receiver container, accumulates the radon that enters through the barrier, which is the sample being tested.

Two continuous radon detectors (DurrIDGE RAD7) with one desiccant unit each (DurrIDGE Drystik 144-ADS-3R and drierite) are used to record the evolution of the radon concentration inside both chambers. The desiccant unit helps to maintain humidity in the chamber below 10 %. The connections between the chambers and the devices are 1.41 and 1.81 mm thick vinyl tubes. A closed circuit is established as the air extracted for radon analysis returns to the chambers. Temperature and humidity are monitored by a weather station (TFA) installed in the laboratory. Fig. 3 shows a diagram of the experimental set-up.

The test begins when the barrier sample is placed between the two chambers and the system is sealed. The radon concentration inside them is recorded at 30-min intervals for 48 h following the methodology previously described in (Ruvira et al., 2022), which explains the modification of the ISO standard made to shorten measurement times. After that, the chambers are flushed, and the devices are purged.

A leakage test was carried out on the chambers, and a leakage rate of 0.0034 h^{-1} was obtained. To carry it out, a high radon concentration ($169 \text{ kBq}/\text{m}^3$) was accumulated and, after that, the radon source was

Table 1
Materials tested description.

Sample	Material	Thickness (μm)	Composition
A)	Liquid packaging board	490.0 ± 12.0	PE, Al and paperboard
B)	Liquid packaging without the board	131.0 ± 36.3	PE and Al
C)	Coffee packaging	155.0 ± 16.0	Metallised PET and PE
D)	Snack packaging	56.3 ± 9.2	PP and Al
E)	Meat packaging	245.0 ± 27.8	Oriented PET (OPET), PE and EVOH
F)	Salad bag packaging	46.3 ± 9.4	Oriented PP (OPP), PS and PE

Fig. 3. Radon diffusion coefficient experimental set-up.

quickly removed and the chamber was closed with a 2 mm thick stainless steel lid. The reduction of the radon concentration was recorded for 12 h and the obtained experimental data were fitted to the exponential curve corresponding to the following formula:

$$C_{Rn}(\text{Bq} / \text{m}^3) = C_0 \cdot e^{-(\lambda_l + \lambda_{Rn}) \cdot t} \quad (\text{eq. 5})$$

Where C_0 is the radon initial concentration (Bq/m^3), λ_l is the leakage rate (h^{-1}), λ_{Rn} is the radon decay constant (h^{-1}) and t is the time (h). By minimising the difference between the theoretical and the experimental curve, the value of the exponent and, thus, the leakage rate was obtained. Since this value is lower than the value recommended by the ISO standard (it should be less than half of the radon decay constant (ISO, 2017), leakage is considered negligible.

The calculation process used follows the instructions given by Annex A.5 'Expression of results' of ISO/TS 11665-13:2017 (ISO, 2017), which is also explained in (Ruvira et al., 2022).

The first step is to calculate the mean concentrations of both containers for the last 24 h so the reduction in radon concentration can be obtained:

$$\text{Reduction}(\%) = \frac{C_{SC} - C_{RC}}{C_{SC}} \cdot 100 \quad (\text{eq. 1})$$

Where C_{SC} and C_{RC} are the mean radon concentrations for the last 24 h in the source and receiver containers, respectively.

After that, the data of the receiver container for the last 24 h are fitted to a straight line and the slope value (p) is obtained to calculate the exhalation from the sample to the receiver container (E_1):

$$E_1(\text{Bq} / \text{m}^2 \text{s}) = p \cdot \frac{V}{S} \quad (\text{eq. 2})$$

Where V is the container volume (m^3) and S is the test area (m^2).

Table 2
Minimum radon resistance of the barriers depending on radon soil concentration and building characteristics (Jiránek and Svoboda, 2017).

	Radon resistance (Ms/m)		
	Low radon area	Medium radon area	High radon area
Building with mechanical ventilation	7	25	50
Building with naturally ventilated habitable rooms	50	150	300

By equating the exhalation values (E_1 and E_2), the radon diffusion length (l) can be obtained by an iterative process:

$$E_2(\text{Bq} / \text{m}^2 \text{s}) = \frac{2 \cdot C_{SC} \cdot l \cdot \lambda}{e^{(d/l)} - e^{(-d/l)}} \quad (\text{eq. 3})$$

Where λ is the radon decay constant ($2.1 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ s}^{-1}$) and d is the sample thickness (m).

Finally, the radon diffusion coefficient can be calculated:

$$D(\text{m}^2 / \text{s}) = \lambda \cdot l^2 \quad (\text{eq. 4})$$

To assess the suitability of the materials to act as a barrier, the radon resistance of the samples is calculated as (Jiránek and Svoboda, 2017):

$$R_{Rn}(\text{s} / \text{m}) = \frac{\sinh d/l}{\lambda \cdot l} \quad (\text{eq.5})$$

The minimum radon resistance necessary for the barriers depends on the radon concentration of the soil and the properties of the buildings, as can be seen in Table 2.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Sample characterization

The images presented in Fig. 4, show the layer configuration of each of the samples and their thickness, which provides information about the material configuration.

The samples are all multilayer and have different thicknesses and materials according to their origin. All of them are films except sample F which is a stable moulded material. The liquid packaging board (sample A) is composed of 4 layers, which correspond with PE (number 1), aluminium (number 2), board (number 3) and PE again (number 4). The usual recycling process has been simulated in which the cardboard is removed, obtaining a 3-layer material composed of PE, (1), aluminium (2) and PE (3) corresponding to the sample (B). Sample (C), corresponding to the coffee packaging, is made of PE (1) and metallised PET (2). The snack packaging (D) is composed of 2 layers with aluminium (1) and PP (2). The meat packaging corresponds to the sample (E) and contains oriented PET (1), PE (2) and EVOH (3). Finally, the salad bag packaging sample (F) is made of PE (1), PS (2) and oriented PP (3). This configuration has an impact on the behaviour of the waste as a radon barrier, as will be shown in Fig. 5.

Fig. 4. Images of the surface and the profiles obtained with the conventional camera (front view), FESEM profile (middle image) and the magnifying lens profile (right image). From left to right and top to bottom: A) liquid packaging board, B) liquid packaging without the board, C) coffee packaging, D) snack packaging, E) meat packaging and F) salad bag packaging. The different number of layers of each sample is marked.

Fig. 5. Evolution of radon concentration in the source container (solid line) and the receiver container (dotted line). The materials are A) Liquid packaging board, B) Liquid packaging without the board, C) Coffee packaging, D) Snack packaging, E) Meat packaging, and F) Salad bag packaging.

3.2. Radon diffusion test results

The experiments were conducted between July–September 2021, January–February 2022, and September–October 2022. The air temperature remains constant at 22.9 ± 2.5 °C.

Fig. 5 shows the evolution of radon concentration in both chambers for all the laminated wastes tested. Since the concentration in the receiver chamber is much lower than in the source chamber, the values must be read on the right Y-axis. Except for the meat packaging (sample E), which has a radon concentration in the source chamber of around 186 kBq/m^3 at the end of the test, all the samples reach a concentration between 750 and 1250 kBq/m^3 in the source chamber. As for the receiver chamber, the concentrations at the end of the test vary between 750 and 15000 Bq/m^3 , with the lowest value corresponding to the test with the liquid packaging board (sample A) and the highest value for the meat packaging (sample E).

Table 3 presents the results obtained for the average concentration in the last 24 h of the test for both the source chamber (C_{SC}) and the receiver chamber (C_{RC}), as well as the radon reduction achieved, the radon resistance of the materials (R_{Rn}), the thickness of the tested material (d), the radon diffusion length (l) and the radon diffusion coefficient (D).

As discussed before, the concentration in the source chamber is much higher than the amount of radon that passes through the barrier and reaches the receiver chamber, indicating that the samples slow down the radon flow. Thus, the radon reduction percentage achieved in the receiver chamber compared to the source chamber is greater than 90% in all cases. However, radon reductions above 99% are obtained for the liquid packaging board (A), the coffee packaging (C), the snack packaging (D), and the salad bag packaging (F), with the highest values for the coffee packaging (99.8%) and the liquid packaging board (99.9%). For the liquid packaging board, this result may be because it has 4 layers of different materials (one of which is aluminium) and also a thickness of $490 \mu\text{m}$, which is much greater than the rest, and it is a multiple barrier to the penetration of radon. As for the coffee packaging, the material is composed of 2 layers and has an intermediate thickness among the samples tested ($155 \mu\text{m}$), so in this case the difference in behaviour may be due to the materials of which it is composed (PE and metallised PET).

For the radon resistances (R_{Rn}) the results show significant differences between the samples with values ranging from 71.6 to 5000.2 Ms/m . Nevertheless, considering the values in Table 2, all tested residual materials comply with the necessary radon resistance requirement for buildings with mechanical ventilation in areas with low, medium or high radon content, as the minimum required resistance for the worst case is 50 Ms/m . Furthermore, the snack packaging (D) and the salad bag packaging (F) could be used in areas with medium radon content and natural ventilation.

The best results for this parameter are obtained for the liquid packaging board (A) and the coffee packaging (C), with values of 1732.6 and 5000.2 Ms/m , respectively. In these cases, and in consideration of the minimum requirements provided in Table 2, would be suitable for areas with high radon content in naturally ventilated buildings, due to their high radon resistance.

Regarding the radon diffusion length, this parameter is much larger than the material thickness, which means that radon can pass through

the barrier before disintegrating for all samples except for A and C. In the case of coffee packaging (C), both values are close, but the diffusion length is slightly lower than the material thickness, and in the case of the liquid packaging board (A) a value smaller than the thickness of the material is obtained, which means that most of the radon disintegrates inside the barrier.

Finally, the radon diffusion coefficients are between 10^{-12} and $10^{-14} \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$ for all the samples tested, suggesting that these laminated wastes can protect against radon as they meet the requirement for radon barriers. Sample C and samples A, D and F have the best diffusion coefficient results, with values of $(3.83 \pm 0.46) \cdot 10^{-14}$ and between $(2.86\text{--}3.55) \cdot 10^{-13} \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$, respectively.

Samples composed of polymeric materials (E and F) show overall lower results than samples with polymeric materials combined with aluminium. Thus, sample E, composed of polymeric materials, gives the lowest values for radon reduction percentage, radon resistance and radon diffusion coefficient despite its thickness. In its composition contains EVOH, which has a low diffusion coefficient (Jiránek and Kotrbatá, 2011). However, in this case the results obtained are not comparable with the pure material. This may be due to the fact that this sample is the only one in the form of a stable moulded material rather than a film, which may cause small micro-cracking of the material as it adapts to the test set.

Then, sample F and sample D have similar values of reduction percentage, R_{Rn} and diffusion coefficient with comparable thicknesses and lower values than sample E. In this case, both samples contain PP in one of the layers, which has been shown to be a good polymeric material for use in radon barriers due to its low diffusion coefficient (10^{-14} (Ruvira et al., 2022)). In addition, sample F contains PS, which also has a good diffusion coefficient of 10^{-13} (Ruvira et al., 2022), and sample D contains an aluminium layer, which provides an effective barrier to radon diffusion.

Finally, there are samples A and C, which contain polymeric materials and aluminium in their composition, and have a thickness of 490 and $155 \mu\text{m}$, respectively. In this case, the presence of a high thickness in sample A, together with a PE and aluminium layer, explains the excellent result obtained. In the case of sample C, the difference in performance is due to the type of aluminium layer. While sample A is an aluminium film in a laminated material, sample C is metallised PET. Metallised PET is manufactured by aluminium deposition using a spray or vapour deposition technique (metallisation). Its main advantages over aluminium foil are higher tear resistance and lower production costs. In addition, it provides better water vapour diffusion values and better protection against sunlight, odours or oxidation (Gorjizadeh et al., 2017; Wazir et al., 2021). These properties also make it suitable for use as a radon barrier.

Sample B shows lower results than expected if compared with sample A despite being a composite material of polymeric material and aluminium. This may be because the cardboard layer has been mechanically removed in a similar way as during the recycling process. This removal causes the dragging of the PE layer to which it is glued and may cause small cracks in this layer, which would explain the low radon resistance and the low diffusion coefficient obtained.

Finally, the results obtained are compared with those of other commercial radon barriers in Table 4.

Table 3

Parameters obtained to calculate the radon diffusion coefficient of the studied laminated wastes.

Material	C_{SC} (kBq/m^3)	C_{RC} (Bq/m^3)	Reduction (%)	R_{Rn} (Ms/m)	d (μm)	l (μm)	D (m^2/s)
A) Liquid packaging board	1055.8 ± 97.0	580.7 ± 148.0	99.9	1732.6	490.0 ± 12.0	411.0 ± 10.0	$(3.55 \pm 0.43) \cdot 10^{-13}$
B) Liquid packaging without the board	748.4 ± 44.1	8985.8 ± 1684.1	98.8	71.6	131.0 ± 36.3	935.0 ± 57.0	$(1.84 \pm 0.22) \cdot 10^{-12}$
C) Coffee packaging	949.4 ± 84.2	1559.7 ± 84.6	99.8	5000.2	155.0 ± 16.0	135.0 ± 5.0	$(3.83 \pm 0.46) \cdot 10^{-14}$
D) Snack packaging	756.5 ± 53.9	4694.2 ± 714.4	99.4	197.7	56.3 ± 9.2	369.0 ± 10.0	$(2.86 \pm 0.35) \cdot 10^{-13}$
E) Meat packaging	186.2 ± 1.4	13676.5 ± 367.6	92.7	102.2	245.0 ± 27.8	1073.0 ± 40.0	$(2.41 \pm 0.29) \cdot 10^{-12}$
F) Salad bag packaging	748.5 ± 36.2	5851.5 ± 1204.8	99.2	158.0	46.3 ± 9.4	374.0 ± 9.0	$(2.94 \pm 0.36) \cdot 10^{-13}$

Table 4

Comparison of the radon diffusion coefficients of the laminated waste materials and commercial radon barriers.

Material	Diffusion coefficient (m ² /s)	Thickness (μm)	Composition	Reference
A) Liquid packaging board	$(3.55 \pm 0.43) \cdot 10^{-13}$	490.0	PE, Al and paperboard	This work
B) Liquid packaging without the board	$(1.84 \pm 0.22) \cdot 10^{-12}$	131.0	PE and Al	This work
C) Coffee packaging	$(3.83 \pm 0.46) \cdot 10^{-14}$	155.0	Metallised PET and PE	This work
D) Snack packaging	$(2.86 \pm 0.35) \cdot 10^{-13}$	56.3	PP and Al	This work
E) Meat packaging	$(2.41 \pm 0.29) \cdot 10^{-12}$	245.0	Oriented PET (OPET), PE and EVOH	This work
F) Salad bag packaging	$(2.94 \pm 0.36) \cdot 10^{-13}$	46.3	Oriented PP (OPP), PS and PE	This work
Sisalex® 871	$(6.21 \pm 0.75) \cdot 10^{-13}$	530.0	PE, polyester fibre and Al	Ruvira et al. (2022)
Politaber Combi 40	$(7.00 \pm 2.00) \cdot 10^{-12}$	>2000.0	Elastomer modified bitumen, non-woven and reinforced polyester felt and polymeric coating	(Chova, n.d.)
Radon Floor	$<1.0 \cdot 10^{-11}$	400.0	LDPE, reinforced polyester felt, LDPE	(Rothoblaas, n.d.)
Radon Barrier Polyester	$<4.8 \cdot 10^{-13}$	4000.0	Non-woven spunbond polyester	(Indexspa, n.d.)
Radon Barrier/V	$\ll 4.6 \cdot 10^{-15}$	4000.0	Fibreglass, Al	(Indexspa, n.d.)

As can be seen in Table 4, the laminated wastes have diffusion coefficient values similar or higher than those of the commercial barriers referenced with significantly lower thicknesses, except for the liquid packaging board (which has a similar thickness).

Comparing the results obtained with the commercial radon barriers, it can be noted that the best material would be one that has as low a diffusion coefficient as possible, that the radon diffusion length is smaller than the thickness, and that the material is thick enough to ensure adequate resistance during manipulation and installation. In its composition, it should have polymeric material and aluminium; if the thickness is low, a metallised polymeric layer is better, and if the thickness of the material is high, an aluminium foil is better.

This result opens up the possibility of using these wastes as radon barriers for indoor spaces, although it is necessary to study their adhesion to construction materials and their assembly. In particular, it would be necessary to determine the radon diffusion coefficient of the joints between the materials, the feasibility and scalability of implementing these materials in indoor spaces and their long-term durability.

4. Conclusions

Multilayer materials are known to be effective in preventing the flow of radon, as commercial radon barriers are made of several layers of different materials. Laminated wastes have a similar structure to these commercial barriers as they are composed of several polymer-polymer or polymer-aluminium layers.

The results obtained are promising since, for all samples, the reduction of radon concentration is above 92%, in most cases being above 99%. Regarding radon resistance, all samples could be used in mechanically ventilated buildings regardless of the radon content of the soil.

When determining the radon diffusion coefficient of various laminated wastes, such as liquid packaging boards or food packaging, the values are below 10^{-12} m²/s, indicating that these wastes are valid for mitigating radon entry into closed spaces. However, the laminated waste that has the best diffusion coefficient is coffee packaging ($(3.83 \pm 0.46) \cdot 10^{-14}$ m²/s). In terms of radon diffusion length, the only materials with a value lower than the thickness are the liquid packaging board and the coffee packaging.

The best laminated wastes to be used as a radon barrier are the liquid packaging board and the coffee packaging as their diffusion coefficients are low, their radon resistances are the highest and they are the only ones whose radon diffusion lengths are lower than their thickness, reaching radon reduction percentages up to 99.9%.

In relation to the materials of these laminated wastes, multi-layered wastes composed of polymeric material (PE or PP) and aluminium (both in foil and metallised) give good results with thicknesses from 150 μm upwards.

These results are positive as they present a preliminary alternative for reusing laminated wastes that are currently difficult to recycle and generally end up in landfills. To be used, these residual materials must be configured in mosaic form to build a uniform barrier, which can be applied in indoor spaces, although more studies are necessary about the implementation of this solution, the performance of the joints and their long-term durability. Reusing this type of laminated waste generated in households as radon barriers would help contribute to sustainable development and the circular economy, as it is aligned with Sustainable Development Goals 11, "Sustainable Cities and Communities", and 12, "Responsible Consumption and Production".

CRedit authorship contribution statement

B. Ruvira: Data curation, Investigation, Writing – original draft, Formal analysis. **B. García-Fayos:** Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Methodology, Supervision, Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **B. Juste:** Conceptualization, Supervision, Writing – review & editing. **J.M. Arnal:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Supervision, Investigation. **G. Verdú:** Funding acquisition, Resources, Writing – review & editing.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

The data that has been used is confidential.

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References

- Chova, n.d. Radon gas barrier <https://chova.com/en/products/anti-radon-barriers/>. EsPlásticos, 2021. La voz del sector de los plásticos en España.
- European Union, 2018. Directive (EU) 2018/852 of the European parliament and of the Council of 30 may 2018 amending directive 94/62/EC on packaging and packaging waste. Off. J. Eur. Union L 150.

- Eurostat, n.d. Packaging waste by waste management operations https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/ENV_WASPAC_custom_2607907/default/table?lang=en (accessed).
- Gorjizadeh, N., Pahlevani, F., Sahajwalla, V., 2017. Metallised plastics waste as a new resource - study of electronic structure and chemical bond. *J. Mater. Environ. Sci.* 8.
- Holmgren, O., Arvela, H., 2012. Assessment of current techniques used for reduction of indoor radon concentration in existing and new houses in European countries. STUK-A251. Helsinki.
- Indexspa, n.d. Radon Barriers https://www.indexspa.it/indexspacom/TECNOPLAN/pdf/RADON_BARRIER-EN.pdf.
- International Standardization Organization (ISO), 2017. ISO/TS 11665-13:2017 - Measurement of Radioactivity in the Environment — Air: Radon 222 — Part 13: Determination of the Diffusion Coefficient in Waterproof Materials: Membrane Two-Side Activity Concentration Test Method.
- Jiránek, M., Kotrbatá, M., 2011. Radon diffusion coefficients in 360 waterproof materials of different chemical composition. *Radiat. Protect. Dosim.* 145, 178–183. <https://doi.org/10.1093/rpd/ncr043>.
- Jiránek, M., Rovenská, K., Fronka, A., 2008. Radon diffusion coefficient - a material property determining the applicability of waterproof membranes as radon barriers. In: *Proceedings of the American Association of Radon Scientists and Technologists, Las Vegas NV*, p. 8.
- Jiránek, M., Svoboda, Z., 2017. A new approach to the assessment of radon barrier properties of waterproofing materials. *Radiat. Protect. Dosim.* 177, 116–120. <https://doi.org/10.1093/RPD/NCX140>.
- Kaiser, K., Schmid, M., Schlummer, M., 2018. Recycling of polymer-based multilayer packaging: a review. *Recycling* 3. <https://doi.org/10.3390/recycling3010001>.
- Khan, S.M., Gomes, J., Krewski, D.R., 2019. Radon interventions around the globe: a systematic review. *Heliyon*, 5, 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2019.e01737>.
- Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD), 2022. Global plastics outlook - plastics use in 2019. accessed April.29.22. <https://stats.oecd.org/index.aspx?DataSetCode=MUNW>.
- Pacheco-Torgal, F., 2012. Indoor radon: an overview on a perennial problem. *Build. Environ.* 58, 270–277. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.buildenv.2012.08.004>.
- Plastics Europe, 2020. *Plastics - the Facts 2020*.
- Rothoblaas, n.d. Radon Floor <https://www.rothoblaas.com/products/airtightness-and-waterproofing/tapes-and-sealants/tapes-and-profiles/radon-floor> (accessed).
- Ruvira, B., García-Fayos, B., Juste, B., Arnal, J.M., Verdú, G., 2022. Experimental estimation of the diffusion coefficient in radon barrier materials based on ISO/TS 11665-13:2017. *Radiat. Phys. Chem.* 193, 109993 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.radphyschem.2022.109993>.
- Spanish Ministry for Transport Mobility and the Urban Agenda, 2019. Basic document DB-HS on health and safety. Section 6 - protection against radon. In: *Technical Building Code*, pp. 138–184.
- Wazir, H., Chay, S.Y., Ibadullah, W.Z.W., Zarei, M., Mustapha, N.A., Saari, N., 2021. Lipid oxidation and protein co-oxidation in ready-to-eat meat products as affected by temperature, antioxidant, and packaging material during 6 months of storage. *RSC Adv.* 11 <https://doi.org/10.1039/d1ra06872e>.
- World Health Organization, 2009. Indoor radon: a public health perspective. *Int. J. Environ. Stud.* 67, 108. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00207230903556771>.
- Xie, M., Bai, W., Bai, L., Sun, X., Lu, Q., Yan, D., Qiao, Q., 2016. Life cycle assessment of the recycling of Al-PE (a laminated foil made from polyethylene and aluminum foil) composite packaging waste. *J. Clean. Prod.* 112, 4430–4434. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2015.08.067>.